

CREATIVE IDEAS AND INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF LINGUOPRAGMATICS OF TOURISM VOCABULARY

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Currently, the tourism industry is an intensively developing sector of the world economy. According to statistics cited in a number of studies, about 180 million people are involved in the tourism business, which is more than ten percent of the total number of workers worldwide. Such a scale of the tourism industry has become an impetus for the emergence of linguistic studies aimed at studying Linguopragmatics of tourism vocabulary.

Today, the tourism industry is undergoing a variety of studies and is undergoing huge changes and development. This industry is attractive to linguists from a linguistic point of view, and to people working in this industry from an economic point of view, due to its poorly studied and “interesting” nature. The life of society and language are closely interrelated concepts, innovations and changes occurring in society are reflected in the language.

The article examines modern creative approaches and innovative research methods in the Linguopragmatics of tourism vocabulary. The main linguistic techniques, pragmatic strategies and technologies used to improve the effectiveness of advertising texts are analyzed. Recommendations for creating competitive content focused on the cultural and cognitive characteristics of the audience are offered.

The modern tourism industry is highly competitive, which stimulates the development of new marketing strategies. Tourism advertising, as the main promotion tool, requires a special approach, including taking into account the pragmatic and cognitive characteristics of the target audience. Linguopragmatics allows us to study how language tools influence readers, motivating them to choose a specific product or service.

The material for our research was advertising tourism texts taken from periodicals, websites of travel agencies and advertising brochures of tour operators.

The purpose of this article is to explore creative and innovative techniques in the linguopragmatics of tourism vocabulary bank, identify their impact on the effectiveness of communication and offer practical recommendations.

The subject of the study is linguistic units that facilitate the implementation of consumer motives and create a pragmatic effect.

What is linguopragmatics?

Linguopragmatics studies the use of language taking into account the age, gender, social status and professional characteristics of the communicants, as well as the specific conditions and goals of the speech act. [1].

As we know, the main task of pragmalinguistics is to study language in its pragmatic function – as a means of influencing the behavior and consciousness of people in the process of communication. Particular attention is paid to the factors that determine the choice of options for expressing communicative intention; conditions that determine the understanding of the communicative purpose of the utterance. This problematic is the subject of pragmalinguistics.

The stated goal and the tasks set determined the use of the following research methods: the main research method is the method of linguistic description. In addition, in the process of

working on the dissertation, we used other methods of scientific analysis: observations, generalizations, comparisons; we also turned to the statistical method.

It is axiomatic that when creating an advertising text, it is necessary to take into account the internal psychological motives of the consumer, to know his deep psychological motivation and priority needs. In other words, when creating a text advertising a tourist trip, it is necessary to have an idea of the personality of the potential client and his preferences. At the first stage of this study, it seems necessary to consider the personal characteristics of the average modern tourist.

Firstly, any trip requires certain financial expenses, and therefore the person who bought it will be interested in the guarantee of receiving the promised services and the price-quality ratio. Thus, the guarantee of the quality of the vacation is of key importance when composing the advertising text, which is especially confirmed in the advertising texts.

Secondly, for a modern person, the motive of prestige is also significant, the opportunity to count oneself among the "select circle" who visited a particular resort.

Thirdly, a person planning his vacation will most likely want to change the environment, spend time in an atmosphere that is as different as possible from what he is used to. Consequently, the motive of an unusual vacation and the opportunity to relax will be no less significant, as noted in the text describing another European resort.

An effective means of increasing the communicative-pragmatic potential of an advertising text is the thoughtful use of various speech acts in their multifaceted interaction. Having chosen tourism advertising communication as the object of study, we consider it appropriate to propose a contaminated classification of illocutionary acts, which allows for the most complete study of the pragmatic features of tourism advertising texts.

Linguopragmatics studies the interaction of language and its functions in the communication process. In the context of tourism vocabulary development, it is aimed at analyzing language techniques that persuade, inform and motivate potential learners. [2].

For example, tourism advertising texts often include:

- Emotional appeals: "An unforgettable journey to the heart of Europe."
- Visual-verbal elements: a combination of text and images to create vivid associations.

- Localization: adapting content to the cultural characteristics of the audience.

Creativity in pragmatic linguo includes the use of unique ideas, metaphors, storytelling, humor, and intriguing questions. For example, the headline: "Are you ready to discover the secrets of the ancient world?" attracts attention due to its emotional and cognitive charge. [3].

Let's list the following innovative approaches in developing tourism vocabulary bank. For example, the use of technologies such as:

- Artificial intelligence (AI): automatic text generation based on audience preference analysis.

- Big data analysis: identifying effective linguopragmatic strategies based on statistics.

- Virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR): integration of interactive technologies to enhance emotional response.

There are such pragmatic strategies in tourism vocabulary development as:

- Personalization: appealing to the specific interests of the client.

Intercultural communication: taking into account cultural differences, which is especially important for an international audience. [4].

In the course of the study, we analyzed more than 100 advertising texts, from which more than 1000 examples of various inscriptive acts were extracted using the continuous sampling method. Based on the results of studying their functioning, the degree of prevalence of various inscriptive acts was calculated, which can be considered a marker of their pragmatic significance. Thus, the most common among all inscriptive acts (46%) were constatives, which are a simple statement that, however, increases the pragmatic potential of the entire message.

Research results:

As the analysis showed, the interaction and convergence of descriptive acts observed in advertising messages has a special pragmatic potential. Often, one text can combine different types of speech acts, giving the descriptive fragment a bright emotional coloring and enhancing its motivating effect. Thus, advertising is one of the most important factors influencing the choice of a tourist product and forcing one to give preference to one or another type of vacation. Consequently, advertising descriptions of tourist trips, compiled taking into account the desires and internal motives of consumers, can influence the choice of a tourist destination and operator.

Recommendations:

- Use cultural and linguistic features to create localized content.
- Include interactive elements (quizzes, stories).
- Experiment with the form of information presentation (short videos, infographics, VR).

Conclusions:

As an object of linguistic analysis, advertising arouses increased interest among many scientists. But despite the fact that numerous articles, dissertations and monographs published both in Uzbekistan and abroad are devoted to this phenomenon, many issues remain unresolved. In particular, the pragmatic aspect of advertising, within the framework of which the problem of speech impact is analyzed, remains poorly studied.

It should be noted that the pragmatics of advertising is a fairly young branch of knowledge, and perhaps that is why there has not yet been a study in the linguistic science of advertising that would claim to fully cover this problem, which is very important for “persuasive” communication.

- The effectiveness of tourism advertising increases with the use of emotionally charged texts adapted to the interests and expectations of the audience.
- Creative strategies such as storytelling and visualization significantly enhance the impact of advertising text.
- Innovative technologies allow you to automate the process of creating and analyzing advertising content, making it more targeted. [5].

The findings from the study show that the linguistic pragmatics of tourism advertising is a field that combines creative ideas and technological innovations to create texts that can not only inform but also inspire. The use of emotionally charged and tailored messages allows companies to stand out in a competitive market, forming long-term relationships with customers.

Linguopragmatics of tourism vocabulary as an example of advertising text pragmatics as a research area is in the process of its formation for several reasons. One of them is the rapid development of advertising, which is a multifaceted phenomenon due to the diversity of its types and forms. [6].

Undoubtedly, each type of advertising requires independent analysis, because its distinctive features are determined by a number of parameters: advertising medium, specifics of the advertised object, composition of the target audience, which in its characteristics can be both homogeneous and heterogeneous. Next, we should name the reason of a purely linguistic nature. As a scientific category, pragmatics is considered a multicomponent formation by its structure, the study of which requires the combined efforts of representatives of related scientific disciplines. All of the above determines the relevance of our work, caused by the need for further study of advertising in the pragmatic aspect, taking into account its species and genre diversity.

As scientists testify, "in the boundless space of all kinds of goods and services, tourist advertising occupies a noticeable place. There are at least two reasons for this. One of them is the active development of Uzbekistan outbound tourism and, consequently, the formation of the ability of Uzbek people to "read" information from tourist advertising. The second is the potential activation of inbound tourism to Uzbekistan and, therefore, the development of the ability of the corresponding domestic specialists to professionally "fit" stimulating information into tourist advertising.

The practical value of the study is determined by the possibility of using its results in university courses on linguistic pragmatics, as well as the theory of speech influence. In addition, the dissertation materials can be useful in compiling special courses devoted to the language and style of modern advertising.

Creative and innovative approaches open up new horizons in the linguistic pragmatics of tourism advertising. Research in this area helps create advertising texts that not only attract attention, but also create an emotional connection with customers, increasing their trust in the brand.

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